

GENERAL MECHANICS

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Abstract

The Schrödinger equation successfully describes quantum systems, predicting behavior and energy levels with high accuracy, however, its failure lies in not accounting for relativistic effects or gravity. Limiting its use in unifying quantum mechanics and general relativity. In this paper we derive a tensor equation that describes quantum systems, predicting their behavior as well as taking into account relativistic effects and gravity. This is done by taking probability as understood in classical mechanics and not as being “intrinsic” as formerly understood in quantum mechanics. The resulting equation gives us a better understanding of the Schrödinger equation, what the “wave collapse” is, furthermore it gives more information about the behavior of gravity in the quantum realm.

Introduction

Quantum mechanics describes the behavior of particles at a very small scale, focusing on probability, uncertainty and wave-particle duality[2]. Gravity, explained by general relativity, deals with the curvature of spacetime caused by mass and energy[1]. These two frameworks clash because of our inadequate understanding of gravity. A better description of gravity is needed before we can reconcile the two frameworks. Gravity, as one of the fundamental forces of nature, has been extensively studied and modeled since the time of Newton. While Newton’s law of universal gravitation provides a robust framework for understanding gravitational interactions, it does not fully capture the nuances of spacetime curvature described by Einstein’s general relativity. This paper aims to bridge these concepts by introducing a vector field representation of gravitational acceleration derived from Newton’s equation. We then explore the implications of this vector field on “the motion of space coordinates,” the resulting spacetime curvature and the wavelike nature of particles.

Chapter 1

SPACETIME

1.1 SPACETIME

Spacetime is inescapable whether you are studying a system in Quantum mechanics or General relativity, so our description of spacetime determines how successful we are in studying the system. We will describe spacetime and motion in spacetime in what I consider to be a redundant description but the pointing out of these obvious things will be crucial in our understanding of the complexities of spacetime. We will describe the following things as follows:

Space: A manifold covered with coordinates.(Note that this is space and not spacetime)

Motion: The process of **continuously** changing coordinates occupied in space.

velocity: The process of **continuously** changing coordinates occupied in space at a constant rate.

Acceleration: The process of **continuously** changing coordinates occupied in space at a nonuniform rate.

Newton's first law of motion: An object that occupies the same coordinates in space for time $\Delta t = l_{rest}$ remains at those coordinates for all time t unless acted upon by a force(This is because both objects, one at rest and one in motion, will occupy coordinates in space but the one in motion will be changing coordinates after time $\Delta t = l_{vel}$, meaning instead of thinking of motion(velocity) as length per unit time, we can think of it as coordinate(s) per unit time and l_{rest} can be thought of as the sub-minimal amount of time the object can occupy the set of coordinates after which it is at rest) and an object in motion remains in motion unless acted upon by a force.

1.2 GRAVITY

In differential calculus, acceleration is defined as the rate of change of velocity with respect to time[4]. Mathematically, it is the second derivative of position $x(t)$ with respect to time t , or the first derivative of velocity $v(t)$. If we take gravitational acceleration $\mathbf{a}(r)$ to be the vector field of acceleration, then we can relate it to a vector field of velocities $\mathbf{V}(r)$ as:

$$\mathbf{a}(r) = \frac{d\mathbf{V}(r)}{dr} \frac{dr}{d\tau} \quad (1.1)$$

$\frac{dr}{d\tau}$ is the r component of the four-velocity vector[1, 6] in spherical coordinates. In general relativity $\frac{d^2r}{d\tau^2}$ is considered as the equation of a geodesic which is a very profound and brilliant way of looking at it, however, we will take a unique perspective of looking at it that follows the spirit of differential calculus. Before we introduce the idea, we will define the speed of light or photons as “**A constant rate of change of spatial coordinates.**” Instead of taking $\frac{d^2r}{d\tau^2}$ as a geodesic[7] we will take it as the acceleration of spatial coordinates (While space remains static, we can imagine the coordinates flowing like a fluid. Emphasis on acceleration of spatial coordinates, spatial coordinates are moving and not space. We can think of space as a manifold on which coordinates are moving on.), meaning a mass in a gravitational field occupies the same coordinates as time progresses, what is observed as the motion of the mass is the motion of the coordinates, the mass remains at rest. The two vector fields $\mathbf{V}(r)$ and $\mathbf{a}(r)$ tell us about the velocity and acceleration of space coordinates at point r respectively.

This approach helps us look at curvature differently as follows: Imagine standing on the moon and firing photons towards the earth (Ignoring the gravitational effects of the moon), if the proper distance between the moon and the earth is L , the photons will only travel a distance L' to reach the earth ($L > L'$). This does not mean the photons move at a faster speed, the rate of change of spatial coordinates of the photons remains the

same, the coordinates themselves will also be moving. We can measure how much space is curved as:

$$curvature = L - L' \tag{1.2}$$

If the photons are allowed to reflect and move back toward the moon, the distance they will travel from the earth will be L'' :

$$2L = L' + L'' \tag{1.3}$$

We can solve for $\mathbf{V}(r)$ using Newton's equation by substituting into equation number 1.1 ($\frac{d^2r}{dt^2} = \mathbf{a}(r)$, $\frac{dr}{dt} = \mathbf{V}(r)$ and $\mathbf{a}(r) = -\frac{GM}{r^2}$).

$$\begin{aligned} -\frac{GM}{r^2} &= \mathbf{V}(r) \frac{d\mathbf{V}(r)}{dr} \\ -\int \frac{GM}{r^2} dr &= \int \mathbf{V}(r) d\mathbf{V}(r) \\ \mathbf{V}(r) &= \sqrt{\frac{2GM}{r}} \end{aligned} \tag{1.4}$$

We will occasionally interchange between the geodesic interpretation (Curvature) and the spatial coordinate motion interpretation since in principle they are indistinguishable.

Chapter 2

QUANTUM GRAVITY

2.1 MOTION AND WAVES

With this interpretation of gravity, we are ready to move to quantum mechanics. Let us consider a thought experiment: Imagine empty space, then you introduce a mass at a point Q, because of causality we know that a point which is a distance s away from the point Q will not instantaneously feel the gravitational field when you introduce the mass, it will take time $t = \frac{s}{c}$ (c is the speed of light.)[6]. When the mass is introduced, we can imagine the vector field forming outwards at the speed of light. Likewise, if after some time we remove the mass from space, it will take time before this effect is felt, we can imagine the destruction of the vector field building outwards at the speed of light. If we periodically introduce and remove the mass from space, we can imagine a wave of "constructions" and "destructions" forming. We do not need to periodically remove and add the mass to spacetime to observe this wave effect, this same wave effect can be observed if we move the mass through spacetime, every time the mass reaches a new set of coordinates a "construction" is formed and when the mass leaves the coordinates a "destruction" is formed, the resulting wave effect will be a Doppler shifted one[7]. We are going to say this wave effect is what accounts for the wave nature of particles, it is a ill-advised assumption to make but let us consider it and find out where it takes us. Consider the electron double slit experiment:

Figure 2.1: Electron double slit experiment

Before the electron can reach the two slits the wave effect has already interacted with the two slits. The electron(s) in this experiment follow the geodesics of the wave effect and an interference pattern is observed on the screen. The same goes for the double slit experiment for photons the only difference being, the photons move at the same speed as the wave effect, so, the first photons to arrive at the slits do not follow any interference pattern, only the latter photons follow the interference pattern. The latter photons interact with the wave effects of the photons that came before. In 2023, Tirole and colleagues[5] carried out a time-separated double slit experiment to investigate the dynamics of time diffraction at optical frequencies, photons being able to interact with the wave effects of past photons explains why there was an interference when the slits are separated in time. If this is true then it should be incorporated in the Schrödinger equation, in the next section we study how this can explain almost everything misunderstood in quantum mechanics and shine some light on the Schrödinger equations.

2.2 The Schrödinger Equation

The Schrödinger equation is a probabilistic equation[2, 3], we will treat it as nothing more but a probabilistic equation by thinking about probability as we would in classical mechanics while keeping our notion that particles

(The electrons in the double slit experiment) follow geodesics. Consider a mass m orbiting the point O with a constant velocity:

Figure 2.2: Mass orbiting a point O

Figure 2.3: The orbit path cut at point P

We can take the path the mass is orbiting on and cut it at point P , straighten it out and plot the velocity of mass against position (The velocity is positional velocity, $v(x)$ it is the velocity at the point x on the line), see Figure 2.4:

Figure 2.4: $v(x)$ vs x . x goes from 0 to 2π

We can now ask the question, what is the probability of finding the mass at some point on the line? (Disregarding the size of the mass, we can think about the probability of finding the mass at a point as its size goes to zero) Because its velocity is constant, the probability of finding it anywhere on the line is the same for all points on the line. Now consider if the velocity of the mass was $v(x) = \beta|\cos x|$ along the path:

What would be the probability of finding the mass at a point x ? It is more probable to find the mass in the region where the velocity of the mass is changing less rapidly or in the region where velocity is slower, in our experiment it is more probable to find the mass in the region where $\cos x = 0$ and less probable where $\cos x = 1$.

It is to be noted that we take the probability distribution here as ψ and not $|\psi|^2$ and $v(x) \neq v(t)$. What is intriguing about this is that if we have $v(x) = |\sin x|$ then $\psi(x) = |\cos x|$, on the other hand if $v(x) = |\cos x|$ then $\psi(x) = |\sin x|$. $\sin x$ and $\cos x$ are derivatives of each other but $|\sin x|$ and $|\cos x|$ are not. The derivative of $|\cos(x)|$ is given by:

$$\frac{d}{dx}|\cos(x)| = \begin{cases} -\sin(x) & \text{if } \cos(x) \geq 0 \\ \sin(x) & \text{if } \cos(x) < 0 \end{cases}$$

If we introduced a peculiar way of differentiating, by differentiating inside the absolutes we can say:

$$|\cos x| = \left| \frac{d}{dx} \sin x \right|$$

$$|\sin x| = \left| \frac{d}{dx} \cos x \right|$$

We will denote this type of derivative by a capital D instead of d , to say:

$$|\cos x| = \frac{D}{Dx} |\sin x|$$

$$|\sin x| = \frac{D}{Dx} |\cos x|$$

We can then write the general equation of probability distribution $\psi(x)$ as:

$$\psi(x) = \alpha \frac{Dv(x)}{Dx} \tag{2.1}$$

For an electron in orbit it does not mean the electron will be accelerating, the electron moves at a constant velocity but the path it is moving on is curved. The most simplest way to think about it is that, if you move a velocity vector along a curved path, curvature will act as a scaling factor for the velocity vector, however, the velocity vector remains the same.

Things get very fascinating if we take:

$$\psi = |\sin(kx + \omega t)| + |\cos(kx + \omega t)| \tag{2.2}$$

If we take our peculiar derivatives of this function:

$$\frac{D\psi}{Dx} = |k|\psi$$

$$\frac{D^2\psi}{Dx^2} = |k^2|\psi$$

$$\frac{D\psi}{Dt} = |\omega|\psi$$

This unrealistic derivatives give solutions to the Schrödinger equation[3] and gets rid of the imaginary parts in the Schrödinger equation:

$$\hbar \frac{D\psi}{Dt} = |E|\psi$$

Meaning solutions to the equation will be in the form of:

$$\psi = A|\sin(kx + \omega t)| + B|\cos(kx + \omega t)|$$

And the velocity function $U(x)$:

$$U(x) = \left| \frac{1}{k} \right| \psi$$

This removes all the negatives and imaginary numbers from momentum operators[3]. The time-independent equation becomes:

$$E\psi = \frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \nabla^2 \psi + V\psi$$

The time-depedent equation:

$$\hbar \partial_t \psi = \frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \nabla^2 \psi + V\psi$$

For the more skeptical minds let us consider it's application in classical mechanics and in quantum mechanics. For a mass moving with a constant velocity:

$$v(x) = A|\sin(kx + \omega t)| + B|\cos(kx + \omega t)|$$

For an accelerating mass:

$$v(x) = \sum_n^N (A_n |\sin(k_n x + \omega_n t)| + B_n |\cos(k_n x + \omega_n t)|)$$

For a mass moving with a constant velocity in classical mechanics, the values for k are large, so:

$$|\sin(kx + \omega t)| \approx 1$$

$$|\cos(kx + \omega t)| \approx 1$$

This is because sizes of classical masses are larger than their wavelengths.

$$v(x) = A + B$$

$A + B$ will be the observable value for velocity. If you could reduce the size of a classical mass to be smaller than it's wavelength, you can get it to behave like a quantum particle. The ratio of the wavelength and the size of the mass is what matters. For an accelerating mass:

$$v(x) = \sum_n^N (A_n |\sin(k_n x + \omega_n t)| + B_n |\cos(k_n x + \omega_n t)|)$$

It would be ignorant in this function to approximate the sinusoidal function to 1. It is easy to think about what $v(x)$ physically means but how do you relate it to $v(t)$ for an accelerating mass?(For a non-accelerating mass $v(x) = v(t)$.)

2.2.1 GENERAL RELATIVITY AND COSMOLOGY

The tensor form of the probability distribution will be:

$$\psi_\nu{}^\mu = \alpha \nabla_\nu U^\mu \tag{2.3}$$

U^μ is the four vector velocity. We now have a totally new way of thinking about probability distribution and can write the Schrödinger equation in tensor form. The tools needed are the tensor forms of $\nabla^2 \psi$ and $\partial_t \psi$.

$$\Delta \psi_\nu{}^\mu = \alpha g^{\rho\beta} \nabla_\rho \nabla_\beta (\nabla_\nu U^\mu)$$

$$\partial_0 \psi_\nu{}^\mu = \alpha \partial_0 (\nabla_\nu U^\mu)$$

If we let,

$$E \psi_\nu{}^\mu = e_\nu{}^\mu$$

$$\begin{aligned}\hbar\partial_0\psi_\nu^\mu &= E_\nu^\mu \\ \Delta\psi_\nu^\mu &= M_\nu^\mu\end{aligned}$$

The tensor form of the time dependent Schrödinger equation becomes:

$$E_\nu^\mu = \frac{\hbar^2}{2m}M_\nu^\mu + V\psi_\nu^\mu \quad (2.4)$$

And the time independent Schrödinger equation becomes:

$$e_\nu^\mu = \frac{\hbar^2}{2m}M_\nu^\mu + V\psi_\nu^\mu \quad (2.5)$$

Where V is the potential energy. The tensors E_ν^μ and e_ν^μ are rank two tensors, meaning there are 10 independent equations. Solutions for a so called particle in a box in one dimension (Let's say x in rectangular coordinates) with no time dependence the equation becomes:

$$\begin{aligned}e_1^1 &= \frac{\hbar^2}{2m}M_1^1 \\ E\alpha\nabla_1U^1 &= \frac{\alpha\hbar^2}{2m}g^{11}\nabla_1\nabla_1(\nabla_1U^1) \\ E\partial_xU &= \frac{\hbar^2}{2m}\partial_x^3U\end{aligned}$$

For our particle in the orbit we took $U = \beta|\cos(x)|$:

$$\begin{aligned}E\alpha|\sin x| &= \frac{\alpha\hbar^2}{2m}|\sin x| \\ E &= \frac{\hbar^2}{2m}\end{aligned} \quad (2.6)$$

Depending on the system we are studying U^μ can take different complicated forms, this will give different shapes for the probability distribution. The tensor E_ν^μ is proportional to the Einstein tensor $G_{\nu\mu}$:

$$G_{\nu\mu} = Xg_{\mu\alpha}E_\nu^\alpha$$

2.3 THE WAVE FUNCTION COLLAPSE

Looking back at the double slit experiment, the idea of a “wave function collapse” becomes slightly clearer with our newly gained information. If you make a measurement of the electron before it passes through one of the slits you will interfere with the geodesics. If you could measure the electron without interfering with the geodesics, you would be able to still see the interference pattern occur on the screen.

2.4 SPIN AND QUANTUM SUPERPOSITION

$$\psi_\nu^\mu = \begin{vmatrix} \psi_0^0 & \psi_0^1 & \psi_0^2 & \psi_0^3 \\ \psi_1^0 & \psi_1^1 & \psi_1^2 & \psi_1^3 \\ \psi_2^0 & \psi_2^1 & \psi_2^2 & \psi_2^3 \\ \psi_3^0 & \psi_3^1 & \psi_3^2 & \psi_3^3 \end{vmatrix}$$

The diagonal components of this tensor tell us about the probabilities in those respective directions whilst the cross components tell us about the probability distribution of how the particle is twisting and turning in certain directions. The cross components tell us about spin and angular momentum. Spin arises as a result of the wave effects, although the geometry is very difficult to imagine. The following experiment can be set up to prove the theory:

A beam of electrons is fired towards the two slits, an electric field is set up in between to deflect the electrons from going through the slits. On the other side of the slits a laser and a screen are set up as shown. The photons fired with the laser are expected to interfere with the wave effects of the electrons fired on the other side of the slits.

Figure 2.5: Wave effect experiment

2.5 QUANTUM ENTANGLEMENT

Holding on to our notion for geodesics, although it is more difficult to visualize the geometry for the spin of particles, we can still use it to hypothesize what and how quantum entanglement is. Quantum entanglement is a result of a force we will call “The Pauli Exclusion Interaction”, this is an interaction like the weak interaction, which prohibits particles from following certain geodesics after they interacted. If two particles interact, they will forever live in each other’s wave effects and we can imagine the wave effect of the particles becoming one (Entangled). After they have interacted, unless the geodesics are disturbed (“measured”) the two particles are intrinsically connected.

2.6 Author’s Thoughts

The author is a 21 year old Electrical Engineering student at the University of Namibia, I do not have any professional training in Quantum mechanics or General relativity while I compose this paper, my knowledge on the topics is driven purely of passion from reading materials from the field, I do not claim to know more than anyone who is trained in either or both of the fields but I would like to express my thoughts and request patience from the experienced reader. I find the whole idea of an equation of probability extremely remarkable. It is counter-intuitive to think that a deterministic equation can give a non-deterministic one, which, among other things is why the Schrödinger equation was extremely hard to comprehend. Classical mechanics makes a lot of sense and I believe all the answers to the things we do not understand is in our own shortcomings to apply Classical mechanics to them. Dark matter is one example, we now know that the motion of masses and energy affects how spacetime curves, this means in addition to the gravitational potential term in the Schwarzschild Metric, the needs to be another term that deals with motion. The additional term will make up for ”Dark Matter”.

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